

Breeding wheat for organic farming: Can the high grain protein gene *Gpc-B1* help to tackle challenges in view of end-use quality?

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ABSTRACT

Organic farming contributes to sustain healthy ecosystems, but challenges such as lower crop yields and supply of the nitrogen needs of crops remain. Wheat is the most important organic arable crop in Europe and grain protein content is the main quality trait also for grading organic wheat despite that high baking quality can be also realized at lower protein contents. Hence, breeding of organic wheat varieties that realize a stable high grain protein content even at lower nitrogen availability is of utmost importance to guarantee income of organic wheat growers. A major QTL for high grain protein content was identified in wild emmer and transferred into bread wheat. We tested six different wheat genetic backgrounds varying for the presence/absence of the functional *Gpc-B1* allele in multi-location trials in Central Europe for their performance under organic growing. The increase in grain protein content caused by the functional *Gpc-B1* allele was present in almost all genetic backgrounds, however, was not consistent across all tested quality traits. None the less, the functional *Gpc-B1* allele may play a major role to increase the stability of organic wheat to reach minimum requirements by traders and processors with respect to grain protein content.

1. Introduction

In 2015, the United Nations (UN) General Assembly adopted the “Zero Hunger” Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) and it was acknowledged that more sustainable agricultural developments are needed to guarantee food security since industrial agriculture threatens pivotal ecosystem services by reducing biodiversity, favoring soil erosion, losses of soil organic matter, greenhouse gas emissions, and eutrophication and pollution of aquatic systems (Blesh et al., 2019). The European Union addressed the UN SDGs with the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy which aims to reduce the input of pesticides and fertilizers by 50% and 20%, respectively, and increase organic farming to a minimum of 25% by 2030 (Box-Fayos and de Vente, 2023). Organic farming and other transformative systems to a greener agriculture have proven sustainability and benefits, but challenges such as lower crop yields and, thus, increased land demand, and supply of crops’ nitrogen needs are evident (Seufert et al., 2012; Eyhorn et al., 2019; Box-Fayos and de Vente, 2023).

Wheat is the most important organic arable crop in Europe. In 2022, organic bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) acreage in the European Union (EU) was 646 665 ha, resulting in a production of over 2.2 million tons, representing an organic share of only $\approx 1.7\%$ of the total wheat production. The main producers are France, Germany, Italy and Romania (Agence Bio, 2023; Eurostat, 2023). In Austria, organic agriculture plays an important role with 22% of the arable land under organic management in 2022. Thereof, bread wheat realized an organic share of 18.6% and 10.5% with respect to total wheat acreage (244 556 ha) and production (1.69 million t), respectively (BML, 2023).

In global wheat trade, protein content and falling number are the most important traits for quality assessment. Grain protein content (GPC) has a major influence on the dough properties and baking volume of wheat flour, although the relationships are rather curvilinear than linear (Gabriel et al., 2017). The global use of GPC as indicator of baking quality is supported by its cheap, non-destructive, fast and reliable prediction via near infra-red reflectance spectroscopy (NIRS).

Although organic agricultural practices vary widely and optimum

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management of crop rotation and nitrogen fertilization can yield protein contents similar to that obtained with synthetic fertilizers, most of the research studies demonstrated that organic wheat has a lower GPC compared to conventionally grown wheat (L-Baekström et al., 2004; Mäder et al., 2007; Ceseviciene et al., 2012; Bilsborrow et al., 2013; Mayer et al., 2015). None the less, marketing thresholds for protein content of organic wheat are rarely different from those for the conventional produce. Only some countries with a higher amount of organic wheat production have sophisticated market requirements. For example, in France the Association of French millers requests a minimum of 10.5% for organic wheat aimed for bread-making. For conventional wheat classes, the requirements are at least 1% higher (ANMF, 2024). In Austria, the usages of the agricultural commodities bourse regulate three market classes of organic wheat with minimum protein contents of 11%, 12% and 13%. Compared to their conventional equivalents these minimum requirements are respectively 1.5% and 2% lower (Börse für landwirtschaftliche Produkte, 2023).

Besides management practices, the selection of the variety is key to reach a GPC required by the processing industry of organic wheat. During the last decades, quantitative trait loci (QTL) and associated molecular markers for GPC were reported for all seven wheat chromosome groups (Kiszonas and Morris, 2018). A major QTL for high GPC was originally identified in wild emmer and later transferred into bread wheat (Mesfin et al., 1999). The functional *Gpc-B1* allele encodes for a transcription factor (Avni et al., 2014) and is associated with a more effective nitrogen remobilization from leaves to the spikes during grain filling, resulting in a higher accumulation of protein in the wheat grains (Uauy et al., 2006a). Homoeologous copies of *Gpc-B1* were identified on wheat chromosomes 6A (*Gpc-A1*) and 6D (*Gpc-D1*), and shown to play a similar role in the regulation of leaf senescence and nutrient remobilization (Uauy et al., 2006b; Avni et al., 2014). A paralogous gene *Gpc-B2* with 91% sequence identity was identified on wheat chromosome 2B (Uauy et al., 2006b). Meanwhile various commercial varieties and genetic stocks carrying the functional *Gpc-B1* allele were developed and their effects on GPC and baking quality studied (Tabbitta et al., 2017). However, none of these studies were, at least to our knowledge, carried out under organic growing conditions.

Therefore, the aim of this research was to evaluate the effect of the functional *Gpc-B1* allele in different genetic backgrounds and under organic multi-environment trials in Central Europe on grain yield, grain protein content, dough mixing properties and baking volume.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant material

Hard red spring wheat ‘Glupro’, developed by North Dakota State University (Mesfin et al., 1999), was crossed to hard red winter wheats ‘Spontan’ (Secobra Saatzucht, Germany) and ‘Mv Kolompos’ (Agricultural Institute, Hungary). F₁ and F₂ generations were multiplied as fall sown crop on the field. Some more than 500 F₃ plants of each cross were finally vernalized, transferred to the greenhouse, individually labelled and submitted to marker-assisted selection (MAS). PCR-CAPS marker *Xuhw89* (Distelfeld et al., 2006; <https://maswheat.ucdavis.edu/protocols/HGPC>) and KASP marker GCP-DUP (Rasheed et al., 2016) were applied for the screening of *Gpc-B1* alleles. The plants were individually harvested and bulked to two populations per cross, being homozygous for either *Gpc-B1a* (non-functional allele) or *Gpc-B1b* (functional wild type allele). Heterozygous plants were discarded.

Additionally, near-isogenic lines (NILs) developed by Sherman et al. (2008) in the genetic backgrounds of US hard red spring wheats ‘Choteau’, ‘Hank’ and ‘McNeal’, and hard white spring wheat ‘Explorer’ were included (Table 1).

Table 1

Wheat germplasm varying for the presence of *Gpc-B1* alleles grown in multi-environment field trials in Central Europe.

Genotype	Accession	Pedigree	Allele
BTX501-PopA		Spontan/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
BTX501-PopB		Spontan/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
BTX502-PopA		Mv Kolompos/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
BTX502-PopB		Mv Kolompos/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS2	PI 651502	Hank*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS3	PI 651503	Hank*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS16	PI 651504	Hank*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS17	PI 651505	Hank*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS26	PI 651506	McNeal*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS27	PI 651507	McNeal*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS36	PI 651508	McNeal*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS37	PI 651509	McNeal*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS44	PI 651510	Choteau*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS45	PI 651511	Choteau*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS48	PI 651512	Choteau*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS49	PI 651513	Choteau*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS223	PI 651514	Explorer*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS227	PI 651515	Explorer*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
06IFAFS225	PI 651516	Explorer*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>
06IFAFS233	PI 651517	Explorer*7/Glupro	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>

2.2. Test environments

The plant material was evaluated under organic field trials in 2022 in Raasdorf, Austria (48.233295, 16.590676) and in 2023 in Hagsdorf, Germany (48.504917, 11.866028); Raasdorf, Austria (48.233194, 16.592088); Borovce, Slovakia (48.577095, 17.729088); Martonvásár, Hungary (47.310462, 18.780602); Ptuj, Slovenia (46.411154, 15.872366), and Fundulea, Romania (44.455574, 26.526022). At all test sites, soil fertility management was done only by crop rotation and no additional fertilization was applied. The US spring wheat genotypes were sown together with the four winter wheat populations between mid and end of October. Harvest was done mid of July. The vegetation period on the test sites varied between 260 and 280 days (Table A.1). Due to limited seed availability and climate conditions, the German and Romanian experiments included only the BTX501 and BTX502 populations, respectively. Heavy thunderstorms caused lodging in Germany and Slovenia, while the trials in Austria (2023) and Slovakia were affected by yellow rust and *Septoria glume* and leaf blotch. The field trials were laid out as randomized complete block or row-column designs with two replications, plot size was between 6.8 and 10 m². Weed management was done by one to two-times harrowing in the tillering stage. Grain yield was determined by weighing the plot yield after harvest and expressed as t/ha.

2.3. Quality analyses

The grain samples were cleaned with a type Mini 200 grain cleaner (Samatec, Bad Oeynhausen, DE) equipped with a 3.5 mm upper-, and 1.8 mm lower sieve. An additional cleaning step was done with a Type 3 air classifier (Baumann Saatzuchtbedarf, Waldenburg, DE). Test weight was determined using a 250 mL chondrometer and calculation of the weight into kg/hL according to a regression formula established on the original conversion tables. Thousand grain weight was evaluated by a Marvin CompactLine machine (Marvitech, Wittenburg, DE); screening for grain plumpness was carried out with a Sortimat (Pfeuffer, Kitzingen, DE) equipped with 2.8 mm, 2.5 mm and 2.2 mm sieves. Samples of 100 g were sieved and the individual fractions were weighed and expressed as percentages.

Crude protein content and grain moisture content were determined on whole-grain samples by a NIRSTM DS2500 L device (Foss, Hilleroed, DK) using the artificial neural network (ANN) calibration models of the manufacturer (ICC Standard Method 159; Determination of protein by near infrared reflectance (NIR) spectroscopy).

Milling of flour samples was performed with an AQC806 4-roller laboratory mill (Agromatic, Laupen, CH) after adjusting 500 g grain samples to a moisture content of 14%. Thereafter, the milled samples were sieved with a JEL 200-II (J. Engelsmann, Ludwigshafen, DE) machine to different sieving fractions. For the following tests, the flour fraction <180 µm was used.

Wet and dry gluten content, and gluten index was determined by a Glutomatic® 2000, centrifuge 2010 and Glutork 2020 system (Perten Instruments, Hamburg, DE) according to ICC Standard Methods 137/1 (Mechanical determination of the wet gluten content of wheat flour (Glutomatic)) and 155 (Determination of wet gluten quantity and quality (gluten index ac. to Perten) of whole wheat meal and wheat flour (*Triticum aestivum*)). Flour water absorption and mixing properties were evaluated with a micro-doughLAB (Perten Instruments) using the default mixing speed of 63 rpm.

Baking tests were performed on 10 g flour samples in baking pans manufactured with 1 mm steel sheet according to the template of Shogren and Finney (1984). Dough was prepared in a Promylograph T3 mixer (Gerätebau Egger, St. Blasen, AT) with 10 g flour, 0.4 g dry yeast (Dr. Oetker, Bielefeld, DE), 0.05 g wheat malt flour, 0.15 g salt, 0.1 mL vegetable oil and water according to the water absorption determined by the micro-doughLAB. The dough was mixed approximately 3 min to a dough consistency of 500 force units. After mixing, the dough was molded between the two plain rolls of an Ampia 150 pasta machine (Marcato S.p.A., Campodarsego, IT) and finally the 3 mm dough sheet was rolled to a small loaf and placed in the greased baking pan (Fig. A.1a). The dough underwent fermentation for 60 min at 30 °C and 85% relative humidity in a GS8 Mini R fermentation chamber (Wiesheu Wolfen GmbH, Wolfen, DE) and was thereafter baked at 220 °C for 30 min in a SD-206 bread maker (Panasonic, Osaka, JP) from which the kneading unit was removed. After 2 h cooling, the loaf profile and volume were determined by a BVM 6600 volume analysis system based on laser topography equipped with a model 661281 hook attachment (Perten Instruments) (Fig. A.1c). Generally, three loaves per sample were processed per baking run unless surplus of flour allowed a second run.

2.4. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out with SAS 9.4 (SAS Institute, Cary, NC) and with Genstat 24th Ed. (VSN International, Hemel Hempstead, UK) software. Analysis of variance followed a mixed linear model approach with ‘genetic background’, ‘*Gpc-B1* allele composition’ and their interaction as fixed effects, and ‘environment’ as random effect. Best linear unbiased estimators (BLUEs) were calculated and significant differences between the *Gpc-B1* allele composition within genetic background was tested by appropriate CONTRAST statements in SAS proc MIXED.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Protein and wet gluten content

The protein content of the germplasm was significantly affected not only by the *Gpc-B1* allele composition, but also by the genetic background and their interaction (Table 2). The increase of GPC by the presence of the functional *Gpc-B1* allele, was most pronounced in ‘McNeal’ (+1.45%), followed by ‘Spontan’ (+1.26%), ‘Explorer’ (+1.2%) and ‘Choteau’ (+0.74%). For ‘Hank’ and ‘Mv Kolompos’ no significant differences were observed between the allele compositions (Table 3). Applying molecular markers to ‘Mv Kolompos’ we have found the presence of favorable alleles in other grain protein QTL, i.e. *Qgpc-2B*, *Qgpc-2D* and *Qgpc-4A* (Jiang et al., 2021). If some of these alleles were replaced by crossing with the *Gpc-B1b* donor ‘Glupro’ or if they are still present in the studied populations was hitherto not checked. However, replacement of some favorable by less favorable alleles could explain the inefficiency of *Gpc-B1b* in this population. For the spring wheat germplasm, the results are in excellent agreement with Sherman et al. (2008) who reported +1.2% in average for the *Gpc-B1b* NILs in ‘McNeal’ and ‘Explorer’, +0.8% in ‘Choteau’ and no differences in ‘Hank’. The similar increase in GPC by *Gpc-B1b* in the two experiments is astonishing, considering the different management systems (conventional vs. organic) and growing areas (Montana vs. Central Europe). Tabbita et al.

Table 2

Mixed linear model analysis of variance: significance levels ($p > F$) of fixed effects for key agronomic and quality traits.

	GPC ^a	GY	TW	WA	DT	VOL
<i>Gpc-B1</i> allele	<0.0001	0.2806	0.3813	0.9235	0.5646	0.1115
Background	0.0156	0.0003	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0142	0.0033
Allele*Background	0.0292	0.6185	0.1007	0.1198	0.2746	0.6999

^a GPC, grain protein content; GY, grain yield; TW, test weight; WA, flour water absorption; DT, dough development time; VOL, baking volume.

Table 3

Best linear unbiased estimators (BLUEs) of key agronomic and quality traits of near-isogenic lines and bulk populations varying for the presence of *Gpc-B1* alleles. BLUEs significantly different within the same genetic background are indicated (†, $p < 0.1$; **, $p < 0.01$; ***, $p < 0.001$).

Background	GPC ^a (%)		GY (t/ha)		TW (kg/hL)	
	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
Mv Kolompos	12.31	12.47	3.251	3.690	77.4	76.5
Spontan	11.75	13.01 **	3.502	3.902	78.0	78.7
Choteau	11.99	12.73 †	3.673	3.844	80.7	79.8
Explorer	12.36	13.56 **	3.220	2.689	79.3	80.0
Hank	12.44	12.21	1.952	2.138	71.9	70.9
McNeal	11.16	12.61 ***	2.953	3.784	73.6	79.3 **
	WA (%)		DT (min)		VOL (cm ³ /100 g)	
Mv Kolompos	58.8	60.4	2.92	3.68	427.2	451.1
Spontan	59.5	60.3	2.96	4.14	377.3	432.7 [†]
Choteau	62.8 [†]	60.8	5.81 [†]	4.11	451.7	443.0
Explorer	64.4	65.1	3.38	4.55	437.0	446.5
Hank	62.1	60.6	3.44	3.33	395.5	409.4
McNeal	64.6	65.3	2.40	2.45	382.0	390.5

^a Abbreviations see Table 2.

Fig. 1. Environmental variation in grain crude protein content (a) and grain yield (b) of European winter wheat populations and US spring wheat near isogenic lines varying for the presence of *Gpc-B1* alleles. Bands indicate Austrian limits for grain protein content of organic wheat market classes (i.e. >11%: milling; >12%: quality; >13%: premium; >14%: ultimate) (a) and average grain yields of organic wheat in Austria in 2022 (3.9 t/ha) and 2023 (4.1 t/ha) (b). Boxes comprise the lower and upper quartile of data including the median (red line); whiskers are extended to the minimum and maximum. Environmental codes represent the ISO3166 country codes (AT, Austria; DE, Germany; HU, Hungary; RO, Romania; SI, Slovenia; SK, Slovakia) and the harvest year (22, 2022; 23, 2023). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

(2017) reviewed 14 studies including a wide range of genetic backgrounds and environments and found that in 90% an average increase of +2.3% was observed. Excluding experiments carried out in India, the average increase is +0.8% and, thus, similar to our study. An average increase of +0.8% to +1.1% was also observed for various Canadian spring wheat germplasm by Bokore et al. (2019) and Brar et al. (2021).

Considering the French and Austrian market requirements for organic wheat, 91.3% and 88.8% of the samples, respectively, would have surpassed the minimum threshold. Even 60% and 42.5% of the samples have surpassed 13% and 14%, corresponding to the Austrian market classes of 'premium' and 'ultimate' wheat (Fig. 1a). Out of these samples, the majority – respectively 58% and 62% – carried the *Gpc-B1b* allele. From Fig. 1a it is obvious that GPC was not only influenced by the genotype, but also largely by the environment. While the Austrian and Hungarian test site realized high levels of GPC, the Romanian, Slovakian and Slovenian sites have shown significantly lower GPC values, in case of Slovakia falling mostly below 11%. For the Slovenian and Slovakian test site the results are not astonishing considering that they were only

recently transformed into organic sites and it will still take some time for conditioning the biological soil fertility (Fließbach et al., 2007). In Slovenia, also excessive precipitation was recorded before harvest in July (Fig. A.2). As demonstrated by long-term data for north-eastern Germany, an increase of precipitation in July during wheat ripening leads to a decrease in GPC (Vollmer and Mußhoff, 2018). Surprisingly low are the GPC levels for the German site which is already organic for long time. At this site, only limited rainfalls (<25 mm) were recorded for five weeks from 18th May onwards, thus, negatively affecting nitrogen uptake during heading, anthesis and early grain filling and finally leading to decreased GPC (Abreu et al., 1993).

Contrary to GPC, no significant allele and background effect was observed for wet gluten content (WGC), gluten index and dry gluten content (Table A.2). Correlation between GPC and WGC, however, is significant and high ($r = 0.85$) (Fig. A.3). Together with GPC, WGC is a popular quality trait for marketing organic wheat in Germany. A minimum of 23% is required for baking wheat, premiums are paid for $\geq 26\%$ and $\geq 29\%$. In the present study, only six samples (7.5%) showed a WGC

below 23% and all of these samples were originating from the low yielding test sites in Germany, Slovakia and Slovenia. Very high levels of WGC were realized by the 'Choteau' NILs (Table A.3).

Considering that *Gpc-B1b* increased GPC but not WGC, we may assume that the wild-type allele has a more pronounced effect on the water and salt soluble protein fractions which are washed off by the Glutomatic procedure. Albumin and globulin proteins were shown to accumulate mainly during the early stages of grain development (Tribošić et al., 2003) which would in turn mean that *Gpc-B1b* is effective already at the very beginning of grain filling. Indeed, Uauy et al. (2006b) and Kumar et al. (2018) showed that expression of *Gpc-B1* starts at early grain filling, reaches its maximum at dough stage and thereafter declines at maturity. Definitely, further studies are necessary to unravel the effect of *Gpc-B1* on quantity and functional properties of the different wheat protein fractions.

3.2. Grain yield

Grain yield was significantly affected by the environment and the genetic background but not by the *Gpc-B1* allele composition (Table 2; Fig. 1b). Low yields in Germany and Slovenia were certainly influenced by lodging due to heavy thunderstorms, test sites in Slovenia and Slovakia were additionally, as mentioned before, not yet conditioned organic soils. Besides, very low yields of some spring wheat germplasm, e.g. in Austria (2022) were likely caused by winter/frost damage as the spring wheats were sown together with the winter wheat populations in October 2021. Contrary, the average grain yield of the spring wheats was similar to the winter wheat populations in 2023. However, variability in grain yield of the spring wheats was significantly greater which is mainly due to an inferior performance of the 'Hank' NILs in Austria. In 2023, a severe infection by yellow rust (*Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. *tritici*) was recorded at the Austrian site. *Gpc-B1b* is known to be closely linked to yellow rust resistance gene *Yr36* (Uauy et al., 2005) and this gene seems to have had some effect on the prevalent race(s), resulting in an average susceptibility score of 4.7 (1 = no disease pustules; 9 = flag leaf completely dead) for the *Gpc-B1a* genotypes, and 3.4 for the *Gpc-B1b* material. While the resistance/susceptibility level was stable in 'Choteau' (2.9 vs. 1.5), 'Explorer' (1.6 vs 1.8), and 'Hank' (8.7 vs 8.3), the *Gpc-B1b*/*Yr36* gene complex improved the resistance level in 'McNeal' (5.3 vs 2.8), 'Mv Kolompos' (5.6 vs 2.9) and 'Spontan' (6.5 vs 1.8). These three genotypes showed also 200–300 kg/ha higher grain yields if *Gpc-B1b* was present (Table 3). For 'McNeal' the result agrees with Sherman et al. (2008), whereas results for 'Choteau' and 'Hank' are contradictory with respect to the resistance of the recurrent parent. However, in view of divergent genetic lineages of yellow rust races responsible for epidemics on the different mainlands this is not astonishing (Ali et al., 2017). The linkage to *Yr36*, which may have an additive effect with other resistance genes against the currently prevalent races is a clear added-value in organic wheat breeding where no fungicides can be applied.

A possible negative effect of *Gpc-B1b* on grain yield due to earlier leaf senescence (Uauy et al., 2006a) seems to be not relevant under Central European conditions where limited rainfall and high temperatures in June and July anyway accelerate wheat ripening. In the present study, slightly earlier heading of *Gpc-B1b* lines was observed in Austria, Germany, Hungary and Slovakia, whereas leaf senescence and ripening was not affected. However, it has to be considered that all trials were carried out under organic management and, thus, no fungicides were used to control leaf diseases such as leaf and yellow rust, and Septoria leaf blotch which also influenced leaf senescence. Although the effect of the allelic composition was not statistically significant, it is noteworthy that, except for 'Explorer', in all other genetic backgrounds the *Gpc-B1b* lines were yielding higher (Table 3). Considering the genetic background, 'Spontan', 'Choteau', 'McNeal', and 'Mv Kolompos' were significantly superior to 'Hank'. Best performing 'Spontan' was also somewhat superior to 'Explorer' ($p = 0.065$). The meta-analysis by Tabbita et al.

(2017) also revealed that in the majority of comparisons (79%) the wild-type *Gpc-B1* allele from wild emmer had no negative effect on grain yield, and in 17% of the comparisons even a positive effect. A drawback observed was the fact that the *Gpc-B1b* donor 'Glupro' increased plant height compared to recipients 'Spontan' and 'Mv Kolompos'. Generally, a certain plant height of organic wheat varieties is favorable in view of competitiveness against weeds, however, in the present cases plant height was about 15–20 cm too tall and, thus, increased susceptibility to lodging.

3.3. Grain traits

All grain related traits (i.e. thousand grain weight, test weight, grain size, grain length, width and their ratio, and seed fractions above 2.8 mm and 2.5 mm, respectively) showed a significant influence by the genetic background (Table 2; Table A.2). For grain width, also a significant influence for the *Gpc-B1* allele composition was observed (Table A.2).

For thousand grain weight (TGW), Tabbita et al. (2017) reported no significant differences for about one-third of the comparisons made in 18 studies, while in 23% an average decrease of 2.2 g was recorded. Here, the decreases varied from 0.5 g in 'Choteau' up to 2.4 g in 'Hank' and 3.4 g in 'Explorer', while for 'McNeal' an increase of 2.9 g was observed (Table A.3). The results are partly contradictory to Sherman et al. (2008) who reported an average increase of 0.65 g for 'Hank' and a decrease of 2 g for 'McNeal'. Although the differences due to the alleles were statistically not significant, it seems that the wild-type allele has a decreasing effect on grain weight in most of the North American and European wheat germplasm, whereas increases in TGW were mainly reported from India (Tabbita et al., 2017). Considering the genetic background, the populations in 'Mv Kolompos' and 'Spontan' showed higher TGW compared to the spring wheat material, however, only the 'Explorer' NILs were statistically significant ($p = 0.0003$ and $p = 0.0274$) from them.

Among grain related traits, correlations were significant and high, especially between TGW, grain size, grain width and seed sieving fraction >2.8 mm ($r = 0.71$ – 0.88 ; Fig. A.4). A significant *Gpc-B1* allele effect was found in the background of 'Explorer' with a decrease of 1.13 mm², 0.15 mm, and 0.25 mm in grain size, grain width and grain length, respectively, if the functional allele is present. Less pronounced was the reduction in 'Hank', i.e. -0.79 mm² in grain size and -0.15 mm in grain width. No decrease, but slight increases in grain size, width and length were observed in 'Mv Kolompos' (Table A.3).

Test weight, grain size and shape are often associated with milling yield. However, Marshall et al. (1986) and Schuler et al. (1995) have shown for Australian and US wheat, respectively, that no one single factor such as test weight is primarily responsible for genotypic differences in milling yield. Hook (1984) studied UK grown winter and spring wheats and also concluded that test weight could not be used for predicting flour yield due to major interactions with growing year and site, genotype and endosperm texture. None the less, test weight is an important criterion in wheat trading, most probably because its determination is cheap, fast and non-destructive. For organic wheat, minimum requirements for test weight are between 76 and 78 kg/hL in France and Central European countries. Lots with lower values are usually accepted at a lower price. In our study, 66.3% of the samples were >78 kg/hL, and 72.5% were >76 kg/hL. Below 73 kg/hL were 18.8% of the samples and almost all of them were from Slovenia and Austria (2023), and two-third of them were related to NILs in 'Hank' and 'McNeal'. In the latter case it is noteworthy that it concerned only lines carrying the non-functional allele, whereas for *Gpc-B1b* lines a significant higher test weight was observed (Table 3). The reasons for this increase in 'McNeal' remain unclear as the review of Tabbita et al. (2017) reported either no influence or a significant decrease averaging 1.56 kg/hL for genotypes carrying *Gpc-B1b*. In the present study, decreases for *Gpc-B1b* lines, but statistically not significant, were observed

for ‘Mv Kolompos’, ‘Choteau’ (−0.9 kg/hL) and ‘Hank’ (−1.0 kg/hL), whereas slight increases were realized for ‘Explorer’ and ‘Spontan’ (+0.7 kg/hL) (Table 3). Correlations between test weight and grain characteristics were significant only for TGW ($r = 0.53$), ratio of grain length to width ($r = -0.47$) and sieving fractions >2.8 mm and >2.5 mm ($r = 0.41$ and 0.67 , respectively). These only medium correlations and the non-significant correlations to other grain characteristics confirms that test weight is only partly influenced by grain shape, but also by kernel density (Yamazaki and Briggie, 1969).

3.4. Dough rheology

Flour mixing properties tested by the micro-doughLAB revealed a significant effect for the genetic background in case of water absorption, dough development time and softening, whereas no effect was significant for dough stability (Table 2; Table A.2).

Flour water absorption was increased by the functional *Gpc-B1* allele by 0.7%–1.6% in ‘Explorer’, ‘McNeal’, ‘Spontan’ and ‘Mv Kolompos’, whereas it was decreased by 1.5% and 2% in ‘Hank’ and ‘Choteau’, respectively. Correspondingly, dough development time increased between 0.05 min and 1.18 min for the four first genotypes, while it decreased between 0.11 min and 1.7 min for the latter two genotypes if the *Gpc-B1b* allele was present (Table 3). However, it has to be noted that the effect of the functional *Gpc-B1* allele was on one side statistically not significant, on the other side not consistent across genetic backgrounds: in ‘Mv Kolompos’, ‘Explorer’ and ‘McNeal’ it improved all parameters, in ‘Choteau’ and ‘Hank’ it deteriorated all mixing traits (Table 3). Rheological and baking studies were rarely done with germplasm varying for the *Gpc-B1* alleles. Brevis et al. (2010) reported a mean change between *Gpc-B1b* and control NILs across six different genetic backgrounds of +2.5% mixograph water absorption. In our study mean water absorption across the six genetic backgrounds remained unchanged, for ‘Mv Kolompos’ it was +2.7% (expressed as percent of the control). Dough properties and baking quality is influenced both by protein quantity and quality. Thus, deterioration in dough mixing traits in some genetic backgrounds might have been caused by the replacement of favorable gluten proteins by less favorable ones. Similarly, Brevis et al. (2010) observed significant interactions between the *Gpc-B1* alleles with the environment and genetic background, and, thus, concluded that baking quality of *Gpc-B1b* introgressions need to be evaluated in each particular genotype and environment. Brar et al. (2021) suggested the combination of *Gpc-B1b* and *Glu-B1a1* (i.e. over-expression of Bx7 subunit) in order to develop bread wheat lines with higher GPC while maintaining dough strength.

3.5. Baking volume

Loaf volume from the micro-scale baking test was significantly influenced by the genetic background but not by the *Gpc-B1* allele composition (Table 2). Loaf volume increased between 8.5 and 55.4 cm³/100 g in almost all genetic backgrounds when *Gpc-B1b* was present (Table 3), however, the increase was only significant at $p = 0.0684$ for ‘Spontan’. As for all dough mixing properties, a negative effect of *Gpc-B1b* on loaf volume was observed for the ‘Choteau’ NILs. The highest loaf volume was observed for the *Gpc-B1b* population of ‘Mv Kolompos’. Generally, the realized loaf volumes in this study are significantly lower than those reported from optimized and/or standard baking tests with higher amounts of flour and are most probably due to a combination of sample size, recipe, fermentation and baking conditions. Similar loaf volumes were reported by Gupta et al. (2022) who studied the effect of *Gpc-B1* in four different Indian wheat genetic backgrounds and also found increased loaf volumes in progenies of only one background.

Correlations between baking volume and rheological properties were not significant with the exception of dough development time, however, in this case the correlation was low ($r = 0.27$). This is contradictory to the study of Gröger et al. (1997) with conventionally Austrian-grown

Fig. 2. Scatter plot matrix of grain protein content (GPC), wet gluten content (WGC), dough development time (DT) and baking volume (VOL). Density plots indicate the variation in wheat samples varying for the presence of the *Gpc-B1* allele (Y = wild type functional allele *Gpc-B1b*; N = non-functional allele *Gpc-B1a*).

wheat where farinograph mixing properties correlated highly with baking volume, especially dough development time ($r = 0.88$). However, it seems that organically grown wheat behaves differently. Kempf (2002) demonstrated that in German official trials wet gluten content was the best predictor of baking volume in organic wheat ($r = 0.75$ – 0.87), while for conventional wheat this correlation was low ($r = 0.27$ – 0.47). In the present study, the highest correlation with baking volume was also realized by wet gluten content ($r = 0.5$) followed by GPC ($r = 0.41$) (Fig. 2). A significant negative correlation was observed between baking volume and gluten index ($r = -0.39$). In another German study with organic wheat, Linnemann (2010) showed that GPC, WGC and dough rheological traits showed a low correlation to the baking volume derived from a baking test optimized for organic wheat. The best predictor of baking volume in this study was the SDS sedimentation volume. Protein quality seems to be more important than quantity in organic wheat as also samples with low GPC realized very high baking volumes. The unclear effects of *Gpc-B1b* on dough rheology and baking performance need further evaluations in different European germplasm and have to consider the variability of popular bread types. As outlined by Brar et al. (2021), the targeted combination of *Gpc-B1b* and other favorable alleles of gluten proteins and MAS may be the means of choice to develop organic wheat varieties with a low risk to fail the respective market requirements for grain protein content and excellent end-use quality.

4. Conclusion

The effectiveness of the *Gpc-B1b* allele on increased grain protein content was shown and, thus, confirmed a wide range of studies hitherto carried out on this issue. However, it was also shown that the allele does not work in all genetic backgrounds. Until now, many QTL for GPC were identified and for some of them additive effects were demonstrated. However, also interaction between QTL might be possible. Although the increase of GPC due to the presence of *Gpc-B1b* might be only 0.7–1.5% in some genetic backgrounds, this may be in the majority of environments sufficient to reach a higher market class and, thus, higher income

for the organic wheat grower. However, it is of utmost importance to (i) exploit *Gpc-B1b* in the most advanced and high yielding breeding material as the germplasm tested in this study was not competitive with the varieties currently most popular in organic wheat production in Central Europe; and (ii) to test and select under the organic target environments as it was demonstrated that the relationship between protein content and baking quality is different under organic compared to conventional management systems and, thus, subject to cross-over genotype by environment interactions (Löschberger et al., 2008; Rolland et al., 2017). Due to the dominant nature of inheritance of the wild-type *Gpc-B1* allele, its exploitation would also work in specific organic breeding strategies such as the development of evolutionary bulks and organic heterogeneous material as theoretically more than 75% of the progenies from F₂ onwards will express the functional allele.

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Data availability

Additional data, tables and figures to those included in this manuscript are available via the Zenodo repository of the ECOBREED community (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790697>).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Appendix

Table A.1

Key data of the multi-environment field trials

Site ^a	Sowing	Harvest	Soil type ^b	T _{avg} (°C) ^c	Prpc (mm)
AT22	October 18, 2021	July 11, 2022	calcic chernozem	9.3	310
AT23	October 17, 2022	July 17, 2023	calcic chernozem	9.5	440
DE23	October 12, 2022	July 19, 2023	eutric cambisol	8.7	474
HU23	October 20, 2022	July 21, 2023	calcic chernozem	10.3	485
RO23	October 28, 2022	July 13, 2023	vermi-calcic chernozem	10.2	353
SI23	October 28, 2022	August 1, 2023	calcaric fluvisol	9.7	810
SK23	October 14, 2022	July 15, 2023	chernic chernozem	8.8	426

^a Environment codes correspond to ISO 3166 country codes and harvest year: AT, Austria; DE, Germany; HU, Hungary; RO, Romania; SI, Slovenia; SK, Slovakia; 22, 2022; 23, 2023.

^b Soil type according to the Soil Atlas of Europe, European Soil Bureau Network, European Commission, 2005.

^c T_{avg}, average temperature from sowing to harvest; Prpc, precipitation from sowing to harvest (data source: Meteostat, Friedberg, DE; nearest weather station <20 km from field site).

Table A.2

Mixed linear model analysis of variance: significance levels ($p > F$) of fixed effects for additional grain and quality traits.

Source	WGC ^a	GX	DGC	TGW	GS
<i>Gpc-B1</i> allele	0.1328	0.6939	0.1155	0.4947	0.0228
Background	0.0130	0.0371	0.1426	0.0010	<0.0001
Allele*Background	0.7300	0.9625	0.9862	0.5274	0.3303
	GW:GL	GW	GL	S > 28	S > 25
<i>Gpc-B1</i> allele	0.1916	0.0099	0.1105	0.9631	0.8671
Background	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Allele*Background	0.7983	0.4602	0.0625	0.1453	0.5976

(continued on next page)

Table A.2 (continued)

	STA	DS
<i>Gpc-B1</i> allele	0.9585	0.4598
Background	0.1605	0.0278
Allele*Background	0.3866	0.8553

^a WGC, wet gluten content; GX, gluten index; DGC, dry gluten content; TGW, thousand grain weight; GS, grain size; GW:GL, ratio grain width to length; GW, grain width; GL, grain length; S > 28, seed sieving fraction >2.8 mm; S > 25, seed sieving fraction >2.5 mm; STA, dough stability; DS, dough softening 12 min after peak.

Table A.3

Best linear unbiased estimators (BLUEs) of additional grain and quality traits of near-isogenic lines and bulk populations varying for the presence of *Gpc-B1* alleles. BLUEs significantly different within the same genetic background are indicated ([†], $p < 0.1$; *, $p < 0.05$).

Background	WGC ^a (%)		GX (%)		DGC (%)	
	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>	<i>Gpc-B1a</i>	<i>Gpc-B1b</i>
Mv Kolompos	29.7	30.2	87.8	90.3	11.97	12.34
Spontan	30.3	32.8	95.2	93.8	10.78	12.01
Choteau	33.6	34.1	92.8	92.4	13.20	14.13
Explorer	29.8	32.4	95.7	96.8	13.14	14.27
Hank	29.3	28.5	96.8	96.2	10.92	11.79
McNeal	24.4	29.3 [†]	95.0	97.4	10.39	12.50
Background	TGW (g)		GS (mm ²)		GL:GW	
Mv Kolompos	41.2	41.5	16.25	16.58	2.08	2.09
Spontan	39.6	38.6	15.64	15.15	1.91	1.97
Choteau	36.7	36.2	15.23	14.81	1.97	2.01
Explorer	34.9	31.5	14.56 *	13.43	2.11	2.10
Hank	37.7	35.3	16.66	15.87	2.08	2.16
McNeal	35.7	38.6	15.02	14.85	1.94	1.93
Background	GW (mm)		GL (mm)		S > 28 (%)	
Mv Kolompos	3.24	3.27	6.67	6.78	65.74	67.67
Spontan	3.32	3.22	6.34	6.30	73.93	71.55
Choteau	3.22	3.14	6.30	6.26	57.64	54.22
Explorer	3.04 *	2.89	6.35 *	6.10	36.40	30.50
Hank	3.30 [†]	3.15	6.76	6.74	51.44	42.24
McNeal	3.22	3.18	6.20	6.13	43.63	61.74 *
Background	S > 25 (%)		STA (min)		DS (FU)	
Mv Kolompos	89.72	91.76	3.49	4.05	115.7	101.0
Spontan	93.67	93.74	5.51	4.76	86.4	88.3
Choteau	91.38	89.87	6.66	4.31	96.4	104.6
Explorer	79.31	77.21	4.25	6.63	87.3	67.8
Hank	76.27	71.50	3.76	3.05	122.9	127.6
McNeal	83.72	92.24	2.74	3.83	107.8	91.6

^a abbreviations see Table A.2.

Fig. A.1. Micro-scale baking test: loaf based on 10 g flour after fermentation (a) and after baking (b); laser topography of the micro loaf (c).

Fig. A.2. Walter-Lieth climate diagram of the 2023 multi-environment trials: (a) Hagsdorf, DE; (b) Raasdorf, AT; (c) Borovce, SK; (d) Martonvásár, HU; (e) Ptuj, SI; and (f) Fundulea, RO. ISO 3166 country codes see [Table A.1](#).

Fig. A.3. Scatter plot matrix of crude protein, wet and dry gluten content. Density plots indicate the variation in wheat samples varying for the presence of the *Gpc-B1* allele (Y = wild type functional allele *Gpc-B1b*; N = non-functional allele *Gpc-B1a*).

Fig. A.4. Scatter plot matrix of thousand grain weight (TGW), grain size (GS), grain width (GW) and seed sieving fraction >2.8 mm (S > 28). Density plots indicate the variation in wheat samples varying for the presence of the *Gpc-B1* allele (Y = wild type functional allele *Gpc-B1b*; N = non-functional allele *Gpc-B1a*).

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